

Insights into Multiple Behavioral Economics from Reaganomics and Its Impacts on the U.S.

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Abstract

This paper argues that current institutional economics is misleading regarding national economic institutions research. Studying leaders, governing parties and governments, and political behavior is crucial. This paper analyzes Reaganomics and its various impacts on the U.S. economy from the perspectives of politician behavior economics, political party behavior economics, government behavior economics, and political behavior economics. In terms of politician behavior economics, in order to obtain political capital and the support of voters, Reagan introduced Reaganomics with an anti-Keynesian image during his election campaign. When in office and faced economic difficulties, he still stuck to his own views to maintain his political reputation and strongly suppressed labor unions to balance relationships among various interest groups. However, short-term political gains masked long-term economic health problems. From the perspective of political party behavior economics, the Republican Party, adhering to conservative ideas and the demands of interest groups, promoted Reaganomics as a banner against the Keynesianism of the Democratic Party. It continued to support it even when the effectiveness of policies was in question to consolidate its political territory. Reagan's policies were consistent with the Republican Party's ideas of a small government and a free market, thus obtaining intra-party support. At the level of government behavior economics, the Reagan administration showed complexity in policy formulation and implementation. Monetary policy theory was disconnected from practice, fiscal policies deviated from their original intentions due to various factors, and there was a lack of systematic planning in deregulation. From the perspective of political behavior economics, the implementation of Reaganomics was closely linked to the U.S. political landscape. During the implementation of policies, alliances were built and Congress was lobbied through political operations. Moreover, policies have been adjusted and redirected in line with changes in domestic and foreign political situations. These four new disciplines are intertwined with each other and together form the logic of Reaganomics' decision-making and implementation. They can be regarded as an important foundation or roots for new institutional economics or institutional economics, which helps to gain a deeper understanding of the political and institutional roots behind economic policies and provides a brand-new perspective and theoretical framework for relevant research and policy analysis. It is important that Reaganomics' supply - side reforms had mixed impacts. Tax cuts had short - term economic stimulus but long-term fiscal problems and increased inequality. Deregulation had some positive outcomes but also caused issues, especially in finance. Long - term, Reaganomics affected the U.S. economic structure, relying on fiscal deficits and the arms race, and lagging in

emerging industries. Fiscal and trade deficits grew, and social inequality worsened with tax cuts and welfare cuts. These impacts highlight the need for countries to consider both short - and long - term effects and economic - social balance in policy - making..

Keywords: political party behavior economy · politician behavior economy · government behavioral economy · political behavior economy · political party behavior economics · politician behavior economics · statesman behavior economics · government behavior economics · political behavior economics · anti-Keynesian · neoliberal economy · institutional economics · new institutional economics · Reaganomics · Reagan Syndrome · economic reform · fiscal deficit · supply-side · economic policy · inflation · tax cut · economic cycles · multiple behavioral economics · economic structure · national governance · political interest

1. Introduction

In the field of economic research, traditional institutional economics has certain limitations when explaining national economic phenomena. The economic operation of a country is not solely determined by abstract institutions but is closely related to the decision-making orientation of core leaders, the implementation of the ruling party's ideas, the policy implementation of government agencies, and the dynamic changes of the macro-political environment. Reaganomics, as an important economic policy framework in a specific historical period of the United States, provides a valuable example for us to deeply study the roles and impacts of politicians, political parties, governments, and political behavior in economic operations.

2. Reaganomics from the Perspective of Politician Behavioral Economics

2.1. Campaign Strategies: Shaping the Image of Change and Spreading Ideas

During his presidential campaign, Reagan keenly perceived the strong desire of the American people for economic change triggered by the "stagflation" dilemma of that time. He skillfully packaged and spread the core ideas of Reaganomics, presenting himself as an anti-Keynesian. Reagan promised to directly increase people's disposable income through large-scale tax cuts, thereby stimulating consumer demand and driving economic growth. Cutting government spending has been portrayed as reducing the financial burden and creating a more relaxed and free market environment for enterprises to promote employment and investment. Deregulation was advocated as a key measure to break industry monopolies, release the vitality of market competition, and stimulate the innovation potential of enterprises. This appealing campaign strategy successfully conveyed the ideas of Reaganomics to the vast number of voters, arousing their expectations for economic recovery and laying a solid public opinion foundation for Reagan to win wide political support and the election victory. For example, in his campaign speeches, Reagan often cited cases where ordinary families lived in hardship due to high taxes and enterprises' development was hampered by excessive regulations, vividly elaborating on the policy propositions of Reaganomics and triggering a strong resonance among voters.

2.2. Policy Decisions during the Administration: Adhering to Ideas and Considering

Political Reputation

After taking office, Reagan faced severe economic challenges. Especially when the U.S. economy suffered a serious recession from 1981 to 1982, with the unemployment rate rising sharply and a large number of enterprises going bankrupt, he still unswervingly adhered to the basic ideas of Reaganomics. Reagan rejected large-scale government intervention measures in the Keynesian style, such as increasing public works expenditures and expanding social welfare programs, which were traditional means to cope with economic recessions. He firmly believed that the free market mechanism had a powerful self-repairing and regulating ability and thought that tax cuts and deregulation could fundamentally stimulate the internal driving force of market entities and promote the natural recovery of the economy. For example, Reagan fully supported the implementation of the high-interest-rate tightening monetary policy by Federal Reserve Chairman Paul Volcker. Although this policy led to a sharp increase in corporate financing costs, a serious setback in investment activities, and a further deterioration of the unemployment rate in the short term, Reagan regarded it as a necessary price for curing the chronic problem of inflation and restoring the healthy and stable operation of the economy, demonstrating his persistent adherence to his own political ideas and strong political determination. Behind this decision, there was not only a deep belief in the theory of the free market economy, but also strategic considerations for maintaining his own political reputation and policy consistency. Once the economic policy ideas advocated during the campaign were easily changed, it might be regarded as political weakness and indecision, thereby damaging his image and prestige in the eyes of voters and endangering the foundation of his political rule.

2.3. Balancing Interest Groups: Suppressing Labor Unions and Supporting Capital

During his tenure, Reagan skillfully used political means to balance the relationships among various interest groups, among which the suppression of labor unions was particularly prominent. Reagan believed that the powerful influence of labor unions in wage negotiations and the protection of labor rights and interests increased the operating costs of enterprises to some extent, weakened their competitiveness, and thus hindered economic recovery and development. In 1981, a large-scale strike by air traffic controllers broke out in the United States. The strikers put forward a series of reasonable demands, such as raising wages, shortening working hours, and improving working conditions. However, the Reagan administration quickly took decisive and tough suppression measures, ordering the strikers to return to work within a very short time, otherwise they would face severe penalties such as being fired and never rehired. In the end, the government fired more than 12,000 strikers who persisted in the strike and imposed severe punishments, arrests, and imprisonment on strike organizers. This landmark event sent a clear and strong signal to the business community across the United States, setting a tough political benchmark for employers in subsequent wage negotiations and labor management, and greatly weakening the bargaining power and political influence of labor unions. Since then, the frequency, scale, and duration of strike activities organized by U.S. labor unions have shown a significant downward trend, and labor unions have been

forced to make substantial concessions in wage and welfare negotiations. In this way, Reagan successfully constructed an interest balance pattern favorable to capital forces and won wide praise and firm support from the business community. However, this approach inevitably led to a relative decline in the economic status of the working class and further widened the gap between the rich and the poor, becoming a long-standing and increasingly sharp contradiction focus in the economic structure of American society.

3. Reaganomics from the Perspective of Political Party Behavioral Economics

3.1. Ideological Consistency: The Flag of the Republican Party's Economic Policies

The Republican Party has long adhered to conservative ideas, emphasizing a small government, low taxes, free market competition, and minimizing government intervention in the economy. The core elements of Reaganomics, including large-scale tax cuts, cutting government spending, deregulation, and promoting the privatization process, are highly consistent with these traditional ideas of the Republican Party, as if tailor-made. On the fierce stage of the two-party political competition in the United States at that time, Reaganomics quickly became a distinctive flag for the Republican Party to oppose the Keynesian economic policies of the Democratic Party. During the previous periods of the Democratic Party's governance, it widely used Keynesian policy tools, such as large-scale government public investment, tax adjustments, and the expansion of social welfare projects, to stimulate economic growth, smooth out economic cycle fluctuations, and ensure social fairness and justice. However, the Republican Party believed that this economic model relying too much on government intervention had led to a series of problems, such as serious inefficiency in economic operations, suppression of market vitality, and an unbearable financial burden. Therefore, the emergence of Reaganomics provided an excellent historical opportunity for the Republican Party to transform its abstract political ideas into specific and operable economic policy practices, vividly demonstrating its unique economic governance model and political philosophy, thereby greatly consolidating the political territory and voter base of the Republican Party and significantly strengthening its position and influence on the political stage.

3.2. Policy Implementation: Consolidating and Continuing Political Interests

Although Reaganomics has exposed many controversies and challenges in terms of policy effects during its implementation, such as the out-of-control fiscal deficit, the continuous expansion of the trade deficit, and the sharp widening of the gap between the rich and poor, the Republican Party still unswervingly and continuously supported its full implementation. From the unique perspective of political party behavioral economics, there are profound political interest considerations behind this phenomenon. Policy continuity is crucial for maintaining the internal unity of the political party, shaping its political image, and strengthening the foundation of voters' trust. Once Reaganomics is easily abandoned, it may be interpreted by the outside world as a sign of chaos in the party's internal policies, a lack of firm beliefs and governance capabilities, which will trigger a large-scale trust crisis among voters and seriously shake the political foundation of the Republican Party. In addition, during the implementation of Reaganomics, the Republican Party formed a complex symbiotic

relationship with the business community, conservative interest groups, and others. The tax cut policy enabled enterprises and high-income groups to obtain huge economic benefits. After enjoying the policy dividends, they actively gave back to the Republican Party by means of political donations, creating public opinion for publicity, organizing political activities, and so on, providing all-round political support for the Republican Party. For example, the business community has formed various powerful lobbying groups and political action committees to spare no effort to influence Congress' legislative process and the government's decision-making direction, ensuring the smooth implementation and long-term continuation of the policies related to Reaganomics. This close interdependent relationship between the political party and interest groups further consolidated the political position and power base of the Republican Party, enabling it to maintain strong competitiveness and influence in subsequent political competitions.

4. Reaganomics from the Perspective of Government Behavioral Economics

4.1. Monetary Policy: The Divergence between Theory and Practice

The Reagan administration claimed to follow the basic principles of monetarist theory in the field of monetary policy, attempting to effectively suppress inflation and achieve stable economic growth and stable price levels by strictly controlling the money supply. However, during the actual policy implementation process, a strange phenomenon of a clear divergence between theory and practice emerged. Although it emphasized tightening the money supply verbally, in fact, it implemented an expansionary monetary policy. Data clearly shows that M1 increased by 34.23% during Reagan's first term compared to the Carter period, and it increased by 45.20% during his second term compared to his first term, both significantly higher than the 30.80% in the Carter period. This expansionary monetary policy ran counter to the established goal of controlling inflation, making it difficult to fully attribute the decline in inflation rate to the monetary policy propositions of Reaganomics. A large amount of money did not flow into the real economy as expected to stimulate production investment and employment growth, but instead poured into the financial market for speculative trading. During the Reagan administration, the Standard & Poor's 500 Index soared, and the average daily trading volume showed explosive growth. The financial markets presented a highly speculative prosperity. Although this serious deviation in the flow of funds alleviated the upward pressure on prices to some extent because a large amount of funds did not directly act on the demand for goods and services in the real economy, it also laid a huge hidden danger for the instability of the financial market. Excessive speculation in the financial market is prone to triggering asset bubbles. Once the bubbles burst, it will cause a devastating impact on the entire economic system. For example, to a large extent, the 2008 U.S. financial crisis was closely related to the long-term excessive liberalization of the financial market and the out-of-control speculative behavior.

4.2. Fiscal Policy: Deviation from Goals and Debt Dilemma

The initial fiscal policy goal of Reaganomics was to achieve fiscal balance, optimize the fiscal structure, and promote sustainable economic growth by cutting government spending and implementing large-scale tax cuts. However, during the actual

implementation process, the fiscal policy seriously deviated from this original intention. On the one hand, large-scale tax cut policies, especially those targeting enterprises and high-income groups, have directly led to a significant reduction in the sources of government fiscal revenue. On the other hand, government spending not only failed to be cut effectively, but also showed a sharp increase in some specific areas, such as military spending. In order to gain an upper hand in the fierce arms race with the former Soviet Union, the Reagan administration did not hesitate to invest huge financial resources in military construction, including researching and developing new advanced weapons, expanding the scale of military forces, and improving military technical levels. For example, during his tenure, the growth rate of military spending far exceeded that of other fiscal expenditures, resulting in an explosive growth of the fiscal deficit. From 1981 to 1988, the cumulative newly added fiscal deficit in the United States reached 1.34 trillion U.S. dollars, accounting for 4.1% of U.S. GDP in each year during that period. The huge fiscal deficit forced the government to rely on large-scale issuance of national bonds to fill the funding gap, resulting in a rapid expansion of the national debt scale. The proportion of national debt to GDP continued to rise from 25.8% in 1981 to 41% in 1989, and the United States gradually changed from the world's largest creditor country to the world's largest debtor country. The continuous accumulation of fiscal deficits and national debts has brought a heavy debt burden on the United States Government. Interest payments have become an important part of fiscal expenditures, further exacerbating the fiscal difficulties and seriously restricting the government's investment ability in other public fields such as education, medical care, and infrastructure construction, posing a serious threat to the long-term healthy and stable development of the U.S. economy and laying a deep hidden danger for the possible outbreak of a debt crisis in the future.

4.3. Deregulation: Lack of Planning and Market Chaos

Deregulation is an important part of Reaganomics, aiming to significantly reduce the scope of federal government's intervention in the economic field, fully stimulate market vitality, and promote free competition and innovation in the economy. However, the Reagan administration lacked systematic planning and comprehensive and in-depth considerations during the process of deregulation. Except for cutting some government red tape and some regulations that were obviously unfavorable to economic development in terms of health and safety, it did not formulate a complete, scientific, and forward-looking overall plan for changing or replacing regulations. For example, only a few deregulation bills, such as the Garn–St. Germain Depository Institutions Act of 1984 and the Cable Television Act, were successfully implemented, while many other deregulation legislations were actually promulgated or in the brewing stage during the Carter era. In the financial field, after deregulation, due to the lack of an effective regulatory framework and risk prevention mechanism, financial institutions, in pursuit of maximizing profits, over-innovated financial products and businesses, resulting in chaos in the financial market order. The competition among financial institutions intensified, and some bad financial behaviors, such as high-risk loans and financial fraud, were common, and the systemic risks in the financial market continued to accumulate. This lack of planning in deregulation not only failed to

achieve the expected goals of improving economic efficiency and promoting fair competition but also laid the groundwork for the frequent occurrence of financial crises in the subsequent development of the U.S. economy, such as the savings and loan crisis in the late 1980s and the more serious global financial crisis in 2008, which were all closely related to excessive deregulation in the financial field.

5. Reaganomics from the Perspective of Political Behavioral Economics

5.1. Policy Implementation: Building Political Alliances and Lobbying Congress

The implementation of Reaganomics was closely linked to the political landscape of the United States. During the policy implementation process, the Reagan administration actively built political alliances and carried out all-round lobbying activities in Congress. Reagan established a deep cooperative relationship with the business community, and the business community became a firm supporter of Reaganomics. Because tax cut policy could directly increase corporate profits, and deregulation provided enterprises with a broader market space and more freedom in operation, enterprises could achieve rapid development through means such as expanding production and mergers and acquisitions. To ensure that the policies could be passed by Congress and implemented smoothly, the Reagan administration organized a powerful lobbying team to actively communicate, negotiate, and exchange interests with members of Congress. They publicized the benefits of Reaganomics to the members of Congress, emphasized the importance of the policies for the economic recovery and long-term development of the United States, and at the same time used means such as political donations and political support commitments to influence the decision-making of the members of Congress. Through this political alliance building and lobbying activities in Congress, Reagan successfully paved the way for the implementation of Reaganomics at the political level, enabling relevant policies to be effectively promoted at the legislative and administrative levels. This political operation mode not only changed the power balance and interest distribution pattern in the process of U.S. political decision-making, significantly enhancing the influence of interest groups such as the business community in political decision-making but also laid a new model foundation for the subsequent development of the relationship between U.S. politics and economy, that is, the formulation and implementation of economic policies are increasingly influenced by the games among political interest groups and the operation of political power.

5.2. Policy Adjustment: Driven by Domestic and International Political Situations

Reaganomics was not static during its implementation, but was adjusted and redirected in a timely manner according to changes in domestic and international political situations. At the international level, faced with the pattern of intense Cold War competition with the former Soviet Union, the Reagan administration closely integrated economic policies with diplomatic strategies. In order to gain an advantageous position in the Cold War, Reagan increased military expenditures and poured a large amount of financial resources into the military field, attempting to enhance the United States' international political influence and geopolitical advantages by strengthening its military power. Such adjustments to economic policies reflected the strategic needs of the United States in the international political

landscape, that is, using economic strength to support military confrontation in order to achieve its political goal of global hegemony.

Domestically, when economic recessions led to a sharp rise in social dissatisfaction and increased political pressure, the Reagan administration would also make certain adjustments to policy priorities. For example, during economic recessions, in order to relieve the social employment pressure, the government would introduce some policy measures to promote employment, such as encouraging enterprises to increase hiring and providing subsidies for employment training. This flexible adjustment of policies reflects the characteristic in political behavioral economics that policies and political situations influence and adapt to each other. Economic policies were no longer formulated solely based on pure economic theories and economic data but were continuously and dynamically adjusted under the constraints and guidance of domestic and international political environments to achieve a balance among political stability, social harmony, and economic development.

6. The Contents and impacts of the supply-side reform in Reaganomics

6.1. Tax Cut policy and its impacts

6.1.1. The Theory of tax cuts stimulating supply

One of the cores of the supply-side reform in Reaganomics was tax cuts. Its theoretical basis was that reducing tax rates could improve the enthusiasm of enterprises and individuals, thereby increasing supply. For enterprises, reducing corporate tax could increase their after-tax profits, prompting them to increase capital investment, expand production scale, and improve labor productivity. For example, enterprises would have more money for research and development, equipment renewal, and hiring employees. For individuals, the reduction in income tax meant an increase in real income, which could encourage individuals to increase working hours or improve their labour skills, thereby promoting economic growth.

6.1.2. Actual impacts and problems

However, in practice, the tax cut policy had complex impacts. On the one hand, tax cuts stimulated corporate investment and personal consumption to some extent, especially with a certain boosting effect to the economy in the short term. However, in the long run, tax cuts led to a sharp increase in the fiscal deficit. While the Reagan administration cut taxes, it did not effectively cut government spending. Especially with the significant increase in military spending, fiscal revenues decreased while expenditures increased, making problem of the fiscal deficit more serious. Moreover, the tax cut policy was considered by some to be "robbing the poor to help the rich" because high-income groups and enterprises benefited more, and the gap between the rich and the poor further widened.

6.2. The Implementation and consequences of deregulation

6.2.1. The Goals and measures of deregulation

Deregulating the government's control over the economy was another important content of the supply-side reform in Reaganomics. Since the New Deal of Roosevelt, the government's control over the economy had been continuously strengthened, and many bills regulating the economy had been issued. After taking office, Reagan deeply

hated government regulations. He believed that excessive regulations bound the vitality of enterprises. For example, on the day he took office, he signed an order to lift national gasoline price controls. Subsequently, he also dealt with regulatory issues in fields such as environmental protection, nuclear energy, consumer products, occupational health and safety, agriculture, radio and television, and financial services.

6.2.2. Results and controversies

Deregulation has achieved certain results in some aspects. For example, long queues outside gas stations quickly disappeared, and oil prices adjusted under the market mechanism. However, overall, there were also many problems. Except for reducing government red tape and some regulations on health and safety that were particularly unfavorable to economic development, the Reagan administration did not have a comprehensive plan to change or replace regulations. In some fields, such as the financial field, deregulation bills such as the disastrous Garn-St. Germain Depository Institutions Act of 1984 brought some negative effects and laid hidden dangers for later financial risks. Moreover, during Reagan's second term, the number of federal regulatory personnel and the budget in some key fields such as environmental protection, banking, and financing actually increased.

6.3. Measures and effects of monetary tightening

6.3.1. Monetary policy and inflation control

Reagan's third measure was to solve the problem of inflation. He adopted Friedman's monetary theory and believed that the sole cause of inflation was an excessive supply of money. To control inflation, Reagan supported the plan of Paul Volcker, the chairman of the Federal Reserve, to achieve the goal of reducing the money supply by significantly raising bank interest rates.

6.3.2. Economic recession and recovery fluctuations

This policy led to a sharp recession of the U.S. economy starting in July 1981 and reaching the bottom in November 1982. At that time, there was a high wave of opposition to this policy in the market, but Reagan insisted on implementing it. Fortunately, starting from the beginning of 1983, the economy witnessed a dramatic recovery. However, this economic recession had a relatively large impact on the U.S. economy. Indicators such as the number of bankrupt enterprises and the unemployment rate deteriorated in the short term, forming the "Reagan Recession". Meanwhile, although inflation rate decreased later, this result was not entirely due to the policy of monetary tightening. It was also affected by a combination of factors such as speculation in the financial market, the decline in commodity prices, and the suppression of the labor union movement.

7. Long-term impacts of Reaganomics on the United States

7.1. Economic structure and development path

7.1.1. Industrial structure adjustment and its impacts

Reaganomics affected the industrial structure of the United States to some extent. Tax cuts and deregulation promoted the development and competition of enterprises in some traditional industrial fields, but were relatively insufficient in cultivating emerging industries. During the period when the global industrial structure was gradually transforming towards high-tech and service industries, the United States

failed to effectively guide the industrial structure to adjust in a more competitive direction through supply-side reform. For example, the development of some emerging industries lagged behind that of other countries, which posed a threat to the long-term prosperity of the U.S. economy.

7.1.2. Changes in the economic growth model

The economic growth model under the impetus of Reaganomics mainly relied on factors such as fiscal deficits and the arms race. The government purchases formed by the huge fiscal deficit played a huge role in promoting economic growth of the United States, but this growth model was not sustainable. Meanwhile, the United States joined the arms race with the former Soviet Union, and military expenditures increased significantly. Although it stimulated related industries to some extent, it also made the economic development overly rely on the military industry, having a crowding-out effect on other civilian industries and social welfare fields.

7.2. Fiscal and debt problems

7.2.1. Fiscal deficit and the scale of National Debt

During Reagan's tenure, the fiscal deficit of the U.S. government grew explosively. When he took office, he promised to balance the fiscal budget, but the result was that he created an unprecedented fiscal deficit in the history of the United States. The cumulative fiscal deficit in eight years was as high as \$1338.6 billion, far exceeding the total fiscal deficit of all his predecessors in 204 years. Since the fiscal deficit was mainly made up by issuing national debt, the scale of the U.S. national debt also expanded rapidly, increasing from 711.9 billion U.S. dollars in 1980 to 2.1 trillion U.S. dollars eight years after taking office. The proportion of public debt to GDP continued to rise from 25.8% in 1981 to 41%. The huge national debt brought a heavy interest burden, which in turn became the main source of the fiscal deficit, forming a vicious cycle.

7.2.2. Trade Deficit and economic balance

After World War II, the U.S. merchandise trade had maintained a surplus for many consecutive years. However, after Reagan took office, the trade deficit grew rapidly. The huge trade deficit forced the Reagan government to adopt trade protectionist measures, but the effect was not good, and the scale of the trade deficit continued to expand. The fiscal deficit and trade deficit became important symptoms of the "**Reagan Syndrome**", having a negative impact on the long-term balance and stability of the U.S. economy and weakening the U.S. position in the international economy.

7.3. Social fairness and the gap between the Rich and the Poor

7.3.1. Tax cuts and cuts in social welfare

When Reagan took office, he implemented large-scale tax cut measures and cut a large number of social welfare programs that supported the poor at the same time. This policy combination further widened the gap between the rich and the poor in the United States. For example, in 1980, the population living below the poverty line in the United States accounted for 11.8% of the total population. By 1983, it had risen to 15.2%, and the number of poor people had reached 35.3 million. This period became the "**lost eight years**" for the poor in the United States, and social contradictions intensified to some extent, having a negative impact on the stability and development of American society.

7.3.2. Long-term social impacts

The widening gap between the rich and the poor had a profound impact on the social structure and social development of the United States. Low-income groups had more difficulty in obtaining resources in education, medical care and other aspects, and the trend of social class solidification had intensified. This situation not only affected social fairness but also might hinder the long-term development of the economy, as the consumption capacity of low-income groups was limited, which was not conducive to the healthy development of the domestic market.

8. Conclusion

From Reaganomics analysis, we can observe that the United States is not a country with a market-oriented economic system, but rather a country with multiple economic components. In fact, the same is true for the United Kingdom, Sweden, Italy, France, Russia, Europe as a whole, China, and the whole world. John Nash once said, "It takes more than 50 years to prove the significance of a great economic theory." The author totally disagrees with this statement. This indicates that when constructing the edifice of economic theory in the past, there was a lack of foresight, and a highly predictable and effective political-economic theoretical system to guide national economic work or global governance was not built. When a country is led by politicians, governed by the ruling party, and forms government institutions to govern the country, the country's social system, political behavioral economics, party behavioral economics, government behavioral economics, and politician behavioral economics should have formed the foundation of various economic disciplines such as institutional economics and new institutional economics. Human society has generally adopted the political system formed by the above model to govern countries and the globe for more than 100 years. Unfortunately, economists have neglected to establish the above four separate new disciplines to study a country's economic system and economic development, which is clearly inappropriate. The significance of such theories does not need 50 years at all to prove its great significance or value, nor even 50 hours. Because once economic theories related to the above four new economic disciplines are proposed, people will immediately feel that the probability of predictable results and the certainty of results will surely be significantly increased if relevant research is conducted, and they will surely play an important role in the economic development and political-economic analysis of a country, multiple countries, or the global economy.

Sometimes, new institutional economics is used to theoretically, morally or academically define whether the institutions of some countries are good or bad. However, from the historical processes that have already occurred, we can see that from the era of Angela Merkel to that of Olaf Scholz, as time passed, the new economic institutions led to a decline in Germany instead. It can be seen that both the definition and positioning of the new institutions are inaccurate, resulting in serious misjudgments among the public and policymakers caused by new institutional economics. For a multi-party country with democratic elections, is the economy under newer economic institutions in more recent years necessarily an economy under superior new institutions? Obviously, when using new institutional economics to

govern a country, there are problems with its theoretical basis, which may very likely lead economists who engage in relevant research to fall into traps and steer national governance down the wrong track. The author of this article deeply feels that in the past, research methods in institutional economics have hindered managers and economic researchers from clearly understanding the essence and origin of institutional economics.

However, institutions of any country are created by politicians, the ruling party and government agencies. The basic social system, politicians, the ruling party, as well as their political propositions and the situation of the government of the country must be taken into consideration first. From Reaganomics, we can clearly see the characteristics of politician behavior economics, political party behavior economics, government behavior economics, and political behavior economics. Therefore, in the past four years, the author has proposed for the first time in the world to establish four new disciplines, namely politician, political party, government, and political behavior economics, and has given corresponding definitions. From this, it can be seen that political behavior economics, party behavior economics, government behavior economics, and politician behavior economics are the origins of new institutional economics. Politicians and economists should study the institutional economy and political economy of countries around the world from the perspectives of political behavior economics, party behavior economics, government behavior economics, and politician behavior economics.

An in-depth analysis of Reaganomics from the perspective of political behavioral economics clearly shows the complex behavioral logic of political actors in the processes of policy formulation, implementation, and impact. The emergence of Reaganomics was the result of the combined action of multiple political factors, and its policy implementation process was full of political games, compromises, and interest trade-offs. This economic policy framework not only had a profound reshaping effect on the US political landscape but also brought about long-term evolutionary impacts on the US economic landscape. Through the study of Reaganomics, we can have a deeper understanding of the close connection between political behavior and economic policies or institutional economy, as well as the interaction mechanism among various interest subjects in the political decision-making process. This has important reference significance for analyzing political and economic phenomena in other countries and periods, and also reminds us to fully consider the impact of political factors when formulating economic policies, so as to achieve the coordinated unity of economic development, social fairness, and political stability.

From the perspective of government behavior economics, an in-depth analysis of Reaganomics can clearly show the motives of the U.S. government's behavior decisions, the policy implementation process, and its wide-ranging and profound impact on various economic fields in a specific historical period. Reaganomics practice not only reflects the government's exploration and attempts in dealing with economic difficulties, but also reveals the complex intertwined relationship between political ideology, party interests, and economic goals behind government behavior. At the same time, this case also fully reflects the importance of the economics of government

behavior as the source of multiple disciplines. Its theoretical and analytical framework can penetrate into various fields such as macroeconomy, industrial structure, and fiscal finance, providing a comprehensive and systematic perspective for understanding the logic of government behavior behind economic phenomena. This is of great significance for the in-depth research on the role and function of the government in economic activities and for formulating reasonable economic policies in different countries and historical periods. It also reminds us that when analyzing economic policies, we must fully consider the multifaceted nature of government behavior and its comprehensive impact on the economy, society, and politics, and avoid simplistic and one-sided understanding and evaluation.

Examining Reaganomics from the perspective of politician behavioral economics, we can clearly see the complex behavioral logic of politicians in the process of formulating, implementing, and adjusting economic policies. During his campaign, Reagan catered to voters and shaped his political image by packaging economic policies. After taking office, he made decision-making trade-offs to maintain his political reputation and balance the interests of interest groups. He promoted policy implementation by building political alliances and lobbying Congress, and adjusted and redirected policies in response to changes in the economic situation and political pressures. These actions of politicians not only profoundly influenced the implementation effect of Reaganomics and Reagan's institutional economy, but also had a far-reaching impact on the political and economic landscape of the United States, including the evolution of party politics, the power restructuring of interest groups, and the adjustment of the economic structure. This analysis helps us gain a deeper understanding of the central role of politician behavior in the process of economic policy and the close interactive relationship between politics and economics, providing useful references and inspirations for studying political and economic phenomena in other countries and regions.

From the perspective of party behavioral economics, Reaganomics is an economic policy system formulated and implemented by the Republican Party of the United States in a specific historical period based on its own political concepts, interest considerations, campaign strategies, and other factors. It not only reflects the economic policy propositions and political goals of the Republican Party, but also embodies the complex behavioral logic and interest trade-offs of the party in the process of formulating and implementing economic policies. Through the practice of Reaganomics, the Republican Party of the United States has achieved its political and economic goals to a certain extent, had a profound impact on the economic development and political landscape of the United States, and also provided a typical case for studying the relationship between party behavior and economic policies or institutional economy.

Nevertheless, it should be noted that there are currently only six types of human social systems, and this classification method has led to cognitive ambiguity among politicians regarding social systems. The naming of the socialist system is inaccurate and its definition ambiguous, resulting in chaos in social governance in some countries. This classification model actually pits Western societies against some Eastern

countries, causing conflicts, confrontations and wars in the global ideological field. In reality, however, the United States and Israel have many similarities with China in terms of social systems. Israel even has many kibbutz communities that are similar to the labor and distribution systems under the communist system. Obviously, the current classification method of human social systems does not conform to reality.

From the perspectives of history and philosophy, the author conducts top-level design for human social systems, creatively reclassifies human social systems on the basis of the current six categories, and for the first time in the world turns human social systems into something like an encyclopedia. This helps to free human social systems from the unclear simple classification and subconscious human social classification system that easily confuses the public in terms of democracy, freedom and human rights, so that ordinary people can clearly identify the political propositions of political parties and politicians in different countries, as well as the political or social systems formulated by them, without being confused by the names of the ruling parties or countries.

The supply-side reform in Reaganomics has had long-term impacts on the United States in many aspects, including impacts on economic growth and industrial structure adjustment, as well as profound changes in fields such as finance, debt, and social fairness. These impacts have both positive aspects, such as alleviating the problem of stagflation in a specific period and promoting the development of some industries, but more negative problems, such as the emergence of the "Reagan Syndrome" such as the fiscal deficit, the trade deficit, and the widening gap between the rich and the poor of the U.S. government. These problems have continuously affected the development of the U.S. economy and society and also provided profound warnings and references for other countries in the process of formulating and implementing economic policies, making countries realize that in economic reforms, it is necessary to comprehensively consider various factors such as the short-term and long-term effects of policies and the balance between the economy and society.

But it is important to realize that the emergence of the term "Reaganomics" in the United States was inevitable, and the occurrence of the "Reagan Syndrome" was predictable. To a large extent, this was because there were no far-sighted people in the United States who could lead the development of ethics, politics, economics, and political economics from a philosophical, historical, and logical perspective, pointing out the correct direction for the political, economic, and social development of the United States and making it acceptable to American society. As a result, whoever is elected president will dominate the political and economic development of the United States, even if they are moving in the wrong direction or constantly caught in the wrong cycle.

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